

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MINISTRY OF BASIC, HIGHER AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION SCHOOL PROGRAMS: BASIS FOR PROGRAM ENHANCEMENT

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The Implementation of Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education School Programs: Basis for Program Enhancement

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Abstract

The study determined the implementation of Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) School Programs as basis for enhancement program for school year 2023-2024 using descriptive-evaluative research design that combined survey and interview in data gathering to 378 respondents. The mean and thematic analysis was used in interpretation of data. Results revealed that the extent of integration of the key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs in terms of inclusivity, equity, right based, rooted in context, integrated and balanced are all highly integrated. The common themes that emerged during interview shows there are minimal problems encountered by the teachers. These included challenges inadequate resources specially technology equipment and competency in using them and integration of lifelong learning as balanced to academic aspects of learning. The study concludes that the MBHTE are effective in the implementation of the key principles of the ministry. The inclusive and equitable school services helped students to feel safe and motivated to go to school. The strict compliance to rights-based education services further ensured children are safe in the school. The rooted concept of implementing the curriculum as mandated by law and the balanced integration of services made the teaching learning promotive of the welfare of the students. However, challenges such as lack of sufficient materials and equipment for technology integration in instruction as well as need for development of teacher competency can hamper the attainment of the goals of school programs. The needs to strengthen the lifelong learning integration in the instruction of teachers can prepare the students to be competitive in the future. The study recommended that the MBHTE must provide allocation to upgrade technological equipment of the schools as part of the urgent programs since this is vital in improving the quality of instruction to the students.

Keywords: *implementation, inclusivity, integration school program*

Introduction

School programs assumes paramount importance in the growth and development of children. The different activities embedded in the program of schools have evolved over the years in different countries all over the world. The transformation in education system from open schools, home-schooling and now even online schooling had made the changes a factor affecting academic development of students. The ability of the school to adapt to changes is a challenge to students, school teachers, and administrators (Babajani et al., 2023).

In the Philippines, the reform in the education system serves as the foundation of school programs. Ensuring that no children are left behind in the school program centered on a balanced, inclusive, and rights-based curriculum. However, despite of the efforts to ensure children are provided with learning opportunities, still the overall performance of children performance on the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2022 Filipino students are 5 to 6 years behind in learning competencies (DepEd, 2023). In order to address these issues, the education sector develops programs to ensure interventions are provided to improve the performances of students.

The Bangsamoro region is not spared of the aforementioned problem. The schools in the region are among the lowest in performance. In order to address this problem, the Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) is determined to deliver balanced, inclusive, rights-based and quality education by creating education policies that reflect the history and aspirations of all Bangsamoro people, implementing programs that produce globally competitive leaders and professionals, and developing informed and empowered citizens through moral governance-based educational programs and policies (MBHTE, 2023).

The Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education (MBHTE) has the largest personnel comprising 60% of BARMM personnel. Due to this large number, the Ministry must address many issues, including high student dropout rates, inadequate school facilities, lack of education services (especially in remote Bangsamoro areas), and ineffective teacher management (MBHTE, 2024).

The conduct of evaluation of the implementation of the Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) school programs can gather vital data that can be a good basis for program enhancement. This can serve as a guide to developing responsive programs.

Research Objectives

The study aimed to determine the implementation of Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) school programs as a basis for program enhancement. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent is the integration of the Key Principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs in terms of:
 - 1.1. inclusivity;

- 1.2. equity;
- 1.3. rights-based;
- 1.4. rooted in context;
- 1.5. integrated; and
- 1.6. balanced.

2. What are the challenges encountered in the integration of Key Principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a mixed-method research design. This design is a combination of qualitative and quantitative, wherein data are collected and analyzed through surveys and interviews.

These designs do not involve manipulation of the primary area of interest by the researcher. Surveys and interview methods are commonly used to gather data for mixed methods of research. Surveys are efficient for gathering large amounts of information about individuals' experiences, beliefs, and attitudes.

This design is descriptive since it offers a comprehensive presentation of the current circumstances and practices in the selected subject of study. Simultaneously, the design is qualitative since it aims to determine the challenges encountered between the integration of the key principles in the implementation of school activities and the success of its implementation.

Respondents

The study involved 378 respondents selected from a diverse pool of participants of teachers within the four chosen divisions of BARMM. These teachers were chosen based on their unique perspectives and central role in the implementation and play critical roles in shaping and experiencing the integration of the key principles in the implementation of the MBHTE school programs, and their direct involvement in the educational program process, their daily interactions with both students and school heads, and their responsibility for executing school-related activities make them critical informants will be invaluable in providing a multifaceted perspective for this research. Through their insights, the study aims to better understand the integration of the key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs and the challenges encountered.

A stratified random sampling was employed to ensure the representativeness of the respondents. This technique allows for the selection of participants from various schools and regions within BARMM, considering factors such as school type and size. The sample size was determined based on statistical considerations to achieve a balance between accuracy and practicality.

The table below shows the distribution of respondents of the study by randomly selecting a subset of participants from a population where each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected. The slovisn formula was employed and presented in the table to identify the sample size.

Table 1. *Distribution of teacher-respondents by Division Level*

<i>Divisions</i>	<i>Schools</i>	<i>Total No. of Teachers</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>
Schools division of Cotabato city (199)	Cotabato City Central Pilot School	189	83
	Sero Central School	102	45
	Rojas Central Elementary School	33	15
	Notre Dame Village Central Elementary School	65	29
	Tamontaka Central School	61	27
Schools division of Maguindanao Del Norte (83)	Broce Central Elementary School	41	18
	Nuling Central Elementary School	35	16
	Simuay Junction Central Elementary School	43	19
	Parang Central Elementary School	68	30
Schools division of Maguindanao Del Sur (70)	Shariff Aguak Central Elementary School	38	17
	Datu Unsay Central Elementary School	24	10
	Kauran Elementary School	38	17
	Tunggol Datu Montawal Central Elementary School	33	15
	Datu Udtog Matalam Central Elementary School	20	11
Schools division of Special Geographic Area (26)	Endaila Silongan Central Elementary School	15	7
	Simsiman Central Elementary School	15	7

	Binasing Elementary School	9	4
	Sambulawan Elementary School	19	8
Total		853	378

Instrument

The researcher utilized a self-developed questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection in this study. This questionnaire was specifically and carefully designed to align with the research objectives, enabling a systematic, relevant and detailed collection of relevant data.

The questionnaire was designed to assess your perceptions and experiences related to the integration of Key Principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs demonstrated by the school principal, teachers, and organizational performance within your school. The responses will contribute to a comprehensive analysis that combines both quantitative and qualitative data to gain a holistic understanding of the implementation of MBHTE school programs.

The questionnaire consists of multiple items that explore the integration of the Key Principles in terms of Inclusivity, Equity, Right-based, Rooted in Context, Integrated, and Balanced in the implementation of school programs. There are also open-ended questions that provide a comprehensive framework for the challenges encountered and coping strategies employed to address the challenges.

Each question in the questionnaire was structured based on a Likert scale, allowing respondents to rate their agreement or disagreement with the statement, thus providing qualitative information about the extent of their perception or practice.

The self-developed questionnaire was streamlined so that the data-gathering process could ensure consistency across all respondents. It also allowed for an in-depth analysis of the integration of the key principles in the implementation of the MBHTE school program.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The researcher used a researcher-made survey instrument that was assessed for validity and reliability. The instrument was validated by checking the three experts for appropriateness for content validity, composed of a college professor from Cotabato State University and two external validators with a mean rating of 4.80, interpreted as highly valid. Meanwhile, a reliability test of the instrument was done through a pilot study of the selected 20 individuals. The result was analyzed by the school statistician using Total Item Analysis with a result of .822 interpreted as highly reliable.

Procedure

The data-gathering procedure involved a structured process of data collection, beginning with obtaining informed consent from participants, school division offices, and MBHTE. Surveys and interviews were conducted to gather insights and relevant information. To start the data collection process, the questionnaires were distributed to the selected sample of school teachers in the BARMM Region. The questionnaires consisted of several closed-ended questions with predefined options for respondents to choose from and were designed to collect quantitative data about the integration of the key principle in the implementation of MBHTE school programs. This format helps ensure consistency in responses and allows for easier data analysis. Respondents were asked to respond to questions based on their perceptions and experiences. The researchers were ensured of consistent data collection and ethical research practices.

Respondents were given adequate time to complete the questionnaire, after which the data were collected for analysis. To ensure credibility and reliability, all responses were kept confidential, and the anonymity of respondents was maintained.

Lastly, the gathered data were then processed and interpreted using statistical analysis for the quantitative and qualitative parts; the gathered data from the conducted interviews were transcribed the information verbatim and used thematic analysis to identify common themes. By using this planned procedure for data gathering, the study will ensure comprehensive, credible, and valuable findings on the integration of the key principles in the implementation of the MBHTE school program.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaire were subjected to rigorous statistical analysis to examine the integration of the key principle in the implementation of MBHTE school programs. The first part of the questionnaire, which focuses on the integration of key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs, utilizes a Likert scale for responses. The Likert scale is an ordered scale from which respondents choose one option that aligns most closely with their view. It is used in this questionnaire to measure the respondents' perception integration of the key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs, including inclusivity, equity, rooted in the context, right-based, integrity, and balance.

The second section was focused on the challenges encountered and coping strategies used.

The researcher planned the in-depth interview with the participants when all of the required letters were authorized. The researcher obtained the name and contact information of the eight (8) participants from selected schools of the different divisions in the BARMM Region.

The researcher met the participants in the classroom where they were being interviewed. Because the school principal stressed time on task, each participant was interviewed with the teacher's vacant time at their most convenient time. The interviews were taped on a cell phone with a headset and back-up by a digital camera.

The researcher transcribed the information verbatim and in order after the interview was completed. It was double-checked by listening to and repeating the recorded audio several times. This is to guarantee that the participants' information is clear and accurate.

Data saturation is achieved using thematic analysis to identify common themes. The researcher prepared a table in which all the research questions and answers will be put and guarantee the secrecy of the participants; coding was used to significant remarks from participants.

The data was entered into statistical software for coding and transformation. This involves translating questionnaire responses into a format that can be processed and analyzed statistically. Descriptive statistics will then be used to summarize the characteristics of the respondents and their views on the integration of the key principles in the program implementation in BARM. This could involve calculating mean, median, mode, frequency, and standard deviation, and could also involve generating tables for clear representation.

The findings were interpreted, and the conclusions, implications, and recommendations from the analysis were drawn. This statistical treatment enabled a comprehensive analysis of the data collected and helped provide answers to the research questions.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the result and discussion of the data gathered.

Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Inclusivity

Table 2 presents the extent of integration of the key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs in terms of inclusivity, which got an overall mean of 4.54, interpreted as highly integrated. This denotes that the school activities are accepting all types of students and is providing instruction that can fit to all types of learners regardless of culture and capabilities.

Table 2. *Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Inclusivity (n = 378)*

	<i>Item The teacher....</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	provides personalized support for students from diverse backgrounds.	4.17	Integrated
2.	fosters understanding and respect among students from different cultural, religious, and social backgrounds.	5.00	Highly Integrated
3.	considers the needs of students with disabilities and other vulnerable groups during emergency preparedness and response.	4.52	Highly Integrated
4.	provides support and resources for students who have experienced disruptions in their education due to conflict, displacement, or other challenges.	4.65	Highly Integrated
5.	provides equitable access to literacy support for students from marginalized communities or with limited resources.	4.08	Integrated
6.	integrates inclusive teaching practices that recognize and celebrate the diverse identities and experiences of students.	4.70	Highly Integrated
7.	engages with local communities to ensure inclusivity and address the specific needs and vulnerabilities of students and families.	4.05	Integrated
8.	facilitates the reintegration of out-of-school children and youth, including those from marginalized groups, into the education system.	4.48	Highly Integrated
9.	collaborates with stakeholders to promote inclusivity and address the diverse needs of students.	4.75	Highly Integrated
10.	offers accessibility of resources responsive to the needs of all students, including those with disabilities, linguistic diversity, and other barriers to learning.	4.97	Highly Integrated
	Overall Mean	4.54	Highly Integrated

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Highly Integrated; 3.40-4.19, Integrated; 2.60-3.39, Moderately Integrated; 1.80-2.59, Less Integrated; 1.00-1.79, Least Integrated

Inclusive education is the practice of accepting, welcoming, valuing, empowering, respecting and supporting all students as a whole child in shared environments and experiences. The best practices discovered in this study provide insight into training, resources, instructional practices, classroom community, and leadership attributes to support inclusive education (Zubia, 2023).

The statement about fosters understanding and respect among students from different cultural, religious, and social backgrounds got the highest mean of 5.00 interpreted as highly integrated. This result means that schools had been allowing students to practice their religious beliefs like prayer time and observance of religious celebrations. This means that education services cut across different culture and religious beliefs which is a common difference among students.

The table further shows that the offering of accessibility of resources responsive to the needs of all students, including those with disabilities, linguistic diversity, and other barriers to learning (4.97), collaborates with stakeholders to promote inclusivity and address the diverse needs of students (4.75), integrates inclusive teaching practices that recognize and celebrate the diverse identities and

experiences of students.4.70 provides support and resources for students who have experienced disruptions in their education due to conflict, displacement, or other challenges (4.65), considers the needs of students with disabilities and other vulnerable groups during emergency preparedness and response (4.52) and facilitates the reintegration of out-of-school children and youth, including those from marginalized groups, into the education system (4.48) are all highly integrated. This means that the school provides learning opportunities to all learners regardless of their status in life including those who are drop outs and the poor.

However, the answer in statements about it provides personalized support for students from diverse backgrounds (4.17), provides equitable access to literacy support for students from marginalized communities or with limited resources (4.08) are all integrated. This means that these are also provided to the students as an opportunity to access education services that can help develop learners to learn and grow.

According to Sloik (2018) there is a need to understand the most effective practices of inclusive education to the current reality at the school sites to be able to understand and respect students culture and religion. Though they came from different religious group the concept of inclusive education of providing learning opportunity to all is a good strategy to motivate learners to attend schooling .

They gave the statement about engages with local communities to ensure inclusivity and address the specific needs and vulnerabilities of students and families with the lowest mean of 4.05 interpreted as integrated. This result means that the school conducts meetings with communities to ensure the local official’s and the people do not discriminate students because of their cultural and religious identity. This can enhance acceptance of different tribes in the community.

Nam (2021) explains that supporting collaboration among stakeholders and policymakers from different backgrounds becomes imperative, allowing multiple perspectives to emerge to create a solution that would benefit all students. This can enhance inclusive education service delivery.

Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Equity

Table 3 presents the extent of integration of the key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs in terms of equity that got an overall mean of 4.58 interpreted as highly integrated. The result manifest eh school provide services based on the needs of each students. The conduct of differentiated instruction makes students from different culture able to adjust their learning styles to the learning activities in the class.

Table 3. *Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Equity (n = 378)*

	<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
	<i>The teacher....</i>		
1.	prioritizes equitable access to quality education for all students, regardless of their background or circumstances.4.00	4.00	Integrated
2.	addresses systemic barriers to education such as poverty, gender inequality, and geographic location.4.47	4.47	Highly Integrated
3.	ensures that resources and opportunities are distributed fairly among students regardless of their socio-economic status.5.00	5.00	Highly Integrated
4.	promotes diversity and inclusion, fostering a sense of belonging and acceptance among all students.4.28	4.28	Highly Integrated
5.	provides support and accommodations for students with diverse learning needs, ensuring their full participation and success in education.4.42	4.42	Highly Integrated
6.	addresses disparities in educational outcomes and strives to close achievement gaps among different student groups.4.70	4.70	Highly Integrated
7.	promotes culturally responsive teaching practices that acknowledge and celebrate the diverse backgrounds and experiences of students.4.95	4.95	Highly Integrated
8.	gives opportunities for marginalized and underrepresented groups to have their voices heard and valued within the school community.4.70	4.70	Highly Integrated
9.	addresses issues of discrimination, bias, and prejudice, promoting a culture of respect and equity among students and staff.5.00	5.00	Highly Integrated
10.	empowers students to become advocates for equity and social justice within their schools and communities.4.82	4.82	Highly Integrated
	Overall Mean	4.58	Highly Integrated

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Highly Integrated; 3.40-4.19, Integrated; 2.60-3.39, Moderately Integrated; 1.80-2.59, Less Integrated; 1.00-1.79, Least Integrated

In the study of Valle-Flórez, et al. (2022) it was reflected that providing equitable access to all students included students with disabilities and coming from all tribes. Schools are trying to address why students with differences in belief and culture should placed in general education classrooms to let them have equal access to education for no one should be left behind.

The respondents answered that addresses issues of discrimination, bias, and prejudice, promoting a culture of respect and equity among students and staff got the highest mean of perfect 5.00 interpreted as highly integrated. This means that discrimination and biases are not acceptable in the school setting and is always not allowed in the school. Everyone is taught to be respectful of every culture and

ethnicity of students and that no one is allowed to belittle anybody due to their identity or culture.

An inclusive school ensures there is no discrimination or bias on its policy. This is needed to implement inclusive education successfully, and school leaders and officials must possess specific attributes that would allow acceptance and protection of all culture of students for effective leadership (Tapia & Polonskaia, 2020).

The table further presents that the statements about it promotes culturally responsive teaching practices that acknowledge and celebrate the diverse backgrounds and experiences of students (4.95), empowers students to become advocates for equity and social justice within their schools and communities (4.82), addresses disparities in educational outcomes and strives to close achievement gaps among different student groups (4.70), gives opportunities for marginalized and underrepresented groups to have their voices heard and valued within the school community (4.70), addresses systemic barriers to education such as poverty, gender inequality, and geographic location (4.47), provides support and accommodations for students with diverse learning needs, ensuring their full participation and success in education (4.42) and promotes diversity and inclusion, fostering a sense of belonging and acceptance among all students (4.28) are all highly integrated. This result shows the consistent provision of services that can be availed by all students. This can make education accessible to all students.

This agrees with the study of UNESCO (2020) that explains that students in all walks of life must feel they are welcome in the school. The differences of students in background can be a factor for discrimination. Therefore it must be considered in providing activities.

But they answered that the prioritizing of equitable access to quality education for all students, regardless of their background or circumstances got the lowest mean of 4.00 interpreted as integrated. This means it is practice in the school. This shows that students are accepted in the school despite of different backgrounds and status in life.

All students must have access to inclusive education. This means educating all students in the same room and supporting them to reach their full potential to lead productive lives (Somma & Bennett, 2020).

Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Right Based

Table 4 presents the extent of integration of the key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs in terms of right based that got an overall mean of 4.63 interpreted as highly integrated. This result manifest the protection and welfare of all learners are given consideration in school service. The assurance of implementing rights based education can means students are safe in the school from abuse and violence.

UNESCO (2020) highlighted that right based education is a mandate to the government. It must be provided to school services. Children who goes to school must feel they are safe inside the school. Teachers must all the time practiced protection of children from discriminations and bias.

The statements pertaining to incorporates principles of human rights education into their curriculum and activities, promotes awareness of children's rights and responsibilities among students, integrates gender equality principles and empower students to challenge gender stereotypes and discrimination, incorporates principles of inclusion and accommodation for students with disabilities, ensuring their full participation and access to education, promotes civic education and empower students to advocate for their rights and the rights of others and promotes respect for cultural diversity and minority rights among students got the highest mean of perfect 5.00 interpreted as highly integrated. It shows that the school had been observing closely the school services and activities to be friendly to the students. It can protect the rights of the students.

This was explained by Participant 2 that the different cultures of the students are considered by every teacher and respects them in their class. They are bleding them all.

This agrees with Francisco, et al (2020) who emphasized that when teachers are guided by the principles of human rights respect the students are guided with the same attitude and actions. Through encouraging students to accept their classmates without stereotyping and discriminations, all learners learn to respect their school mates and interact with them harmoniously.

Also, the table shows that it addresses issues of child labor, child abuse, and exploitation through education and awareness-raising initiatives (4.72), addresses issues of social justice and promotes active citizenship among students (4.65) and encourages the integration of rights-based perspectives into their teaching practices and classroom discussions (4.28) are all highly integrated. This implies that the students rights are proected. This can increase students to have information about their rights and the rights of other people.

However, the fostering of a safe and inclusive learning environment where every student's rights are respected and protected got the lowest mean of 3.77 interpreted as integrated. Though it got the lowest mean still it shows it is implemented. Although due to limited resources sometimes classroom are not fully equipped to provide all the comforts for all the needs of the students but in terms of safety they are well provided.

It was explained by one participant who shared that limited resources in the classroom. Though they wanted to provide all learning materials due to limited budget they have to make use of whatever is available in the school.

Eduardo, et al (2021) emphasized that learning environment must be conducive for learning to all learners. The provision of comfortable classroom and instructional delivery that can provide motivational participation to all students is a good learning environment that can be accessed of all students as their basic right.

Table 4. *Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Right Based (n = 378)*

	<i>Item The teacher....</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	incorporates principles of human rights education into their curriculum and activities.	5.00	Highly Integrated
2.	promotes awareness of children's rights and responsibilities among students.	5.00	Highly Integrated
3.	integrates gender equality principles and empower students to challenge gender stereotypes and discrimination.	5.00	Highly Integrated
4.	fosters a safe and inclusive learning environment where every student's rights are respected and protected.	3.77	Integrated
5.	addresses issues of child labor, child abuse, and exploitation through education and awareness-raising initiatives.	4.72	Highly Integrated
6.	incorporates principles of inclusion and accommodation for students with disabilities, ensuring their full participation and access to education.	5.00	Highly Integrated
7.	promotes civic education and empower students to advocate for their rights and the rights of others.	5.00	Highly Integrated
8.	promotes respect for cultural diversity and minority rights among students.	5.00	Highly Integrated
9.	addresses issues of social justice and promotes active citizenship among students.	4.65	Highly Integrated
10.	encourages the integration of rights-based perspectives into their teaching practices and classroom discussions.	4.28	Highly Integrated
	Overall Mean	4.63	Highly Integrated

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Highly Integrated; 3.40-4.19, Integrated; 2.60-3.39, Moderately Integrated; 1.80-2.59, Less Integrated; 1.00-1.79, Least Integrated

Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Rooted in Context

Table 5 presents the extent of integration of the key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs in terms of rooted in context that got an overall mean of 4.61 interpreted as highly integrated. This result manifest the collective effort of all sectors in education to include in their support and services the consideration of providing inclusive education. This means all students from different culture and tribes are considered to be amenable to the kind of support extended.

Table 5. *Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Rooted in Context (n = 378)*

	<i>Item The teacher....</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	incorporates local culture and traditions into their curriculum and activities.	4.45	Highly Integrated
2.	emphasizes the importance of understanding the socio-economic context of the local community in their educational initiatives.	4.72	Highly Integrated
3.	integrates indigenous knowledge and practices into the teaching and learning process to enhance students' cultural awareness.	4.47	Highly Integrated
4.	promotes community engagement and collaboration in the design and implementation of educational initiatives.	5.00	Highly Integrated
5.	addresses local environmental challenges and promote sustainability practices within the community.	4.83	Highly Integrated
6.	integrates local languages and dialects into the curriculum to promote linguistic diversity and inclusion.	4.85	Highly Integrated
7.	encourages students to explore and analyze local issues and challenges, fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	4.23	Highly Integrated
8.	promotes social cohesion and mutual respect among students from diverse backgrounds within the local context.	4.95	Highly Integrated
9.	incorporates local history and heritage into the educational experiences of students, fostering a sense of pride and identity.	4.00	Integrated
10.	develops culturally responsive teaching practices that resonate with the lived experiences of students in the local community.	4.00	Integrated
	Overall Mean	4.61	Highly Integrated

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Highly Integrated; 3.40-4.19, Integrated; 2.60-3.39, Moderately Integrated; 1.80-2.59, Less Integrated; 1.00-1.79, Least Integrated

Same idea was expressed by Somma and Bennett (2020) who stated that context of schools must align with education goals. The assurance of school offering quality education to learners can help achieved the education goals. The context of learning activities and policies must be harmonized centered towards cultivating students to be productive citizens in the community and nation.

The respondents answered that promotion of community engagement and collaboration in the design and implementation of educational initiatives with the highest mean of 5.00 interpreted as highly integrated. This confirms that the schools have been involving the

community towards ensuring education can be fitted and accessible to the different types of learners. This shows the school advocates to the community the acceptance of students coming from different status in life.

In the study of Nam (2021) the support of government agencies to ensure inclusive education is implemented results to capability building of the school. This made services more extensive and accountability to be a collective effort of stakeholders. This can strengthen the inclusive education provision.

The table presents the statement about it promotes social cohesion and mutual respect among students from diverse backgrounds within the local context (4.95), integrates local languages and dialects into the curriculum to promote linguistic diversity and inclusion (4.85), addresses local environmental challenges and promote sustainability practices within the community (4.83), emphasizes the importance of understanding the socio-economic context of the local community in their educational initiatives (4.72), integrates indigenous knowledge and practices into the teaching and learning process to enhance students' cultural awareness (4.47), incorporates local culture and traditions into their curriculum and activities (4.45) and encourages students to explore and analyze local issues and challenges, fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills (4.23) are all highly integrated. The answer signifies that the curriculum provided to the students corroborates with the activities of the teachers in the class. This can ensure students activities are promotive of development in physical, mental and social aspect.

While statements about incorporates local history and heritage into the educational experiences of students, fostering a sense of pride and identity and develops culturally responsive teaching practices that resonate with the lived experiences of students in the local community got the lowest mean of 4.00 interpreted as integrated. This means that part of the school topics cultivate the rich and vast culture of the students. The students are taught how to love and be proud of their cultural identity to let them feel honored of their culture and tribe.

According to participant 4 the teachers include in their lecture the history of the students culture specially in ancestral domains, however, if teachers are not IP not all of them knows about this history.

Stevens (2020) explains the benefits of talking with the students of their culture and traditions for teachers are cultivating participative discussions on the common cultures of the class. This can express acceptance of their culture that can make the students proud of themselves.

Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Integrated

Table 6 presents the extent of integration of the key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs in terms of integrated that got an overall mean of 4.58 interpreted as highly integrated. This result means that schools are align with the guidelines of school in school priorities. This can make education competitive with change in society.

According to Mitchell, et al (2017) education must be competitive to the change in society. It must be integrated with modernization such as innovations in instruction, rights-based and child centered. This can meet the demand of society and make the learners ready to be part of the evolving community.

All the respondents answered that the school fosters creativity, innovation, and problem-solving skills among students through integrated learning approaches, integrates social-emotional learning and character education into academic instruction to support students' holistic development and encourages to collaborate across disciplines and integrate different perspectives into their teaching practices that got the highest mean of perfect 5.00 interpreted as highly integrated. This result shows the schools had indeed been actively integrating the mandates of involving stakeholders for a collective service. Likewise it included programs and activities that can promote learning in a holistic approach developing student physically, mentally and socially. This can prepare them to the future.

This was confirmed by Participant 3 who expalied that part of teachers program included creative projects which can motivate learners to design their own creativity.

The table further presents that the statement about incorporates real-world applications and practical experiences to enhance student learning (4.98), incorporates community-based learning experiences and partnerships with local organizations (4.93), integrates interdisciplinary approaches in teaching and learning activities (4.23) are all highly integrated. This means that a collaborative learning activity is implemented to ensure students arer connected with community.

But the statement about it promotes cross-curricular connections and integration of knowledge across different subjects (4.00), encourages project-based learning and hands-on experiences to deepen students' understanding of concepts (4.00) and integrates career readiness and vocational training opportunities into the curriculum to equip students with practical skills (4.00) are all integrated. This result signifies that the teachers are using different learning modes. This can be beneficial to the students for it can meet different types of learners.

According to Smith (2023) a holistic context of the curriculum is an innovative approach to teaching and educating students. It addresses the social, ethical, and academic needs of students in an integrated learning format. In this approach, the emphasis is placed on creating a positive learning environment and whole-child support. It includes academic and non-academic needs or wrap-around support to students.

Table 6. *Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Integrated (n = 378)*

	<i>Item The teacher....</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	integrates interdisciplinary approaches in teaching and learning activities.	4.23	Highly Integrated
2.	incorporates real-world applications and practical experiences to enhance student learning.	4.98	Highly Integrated
3.	integrates technology and digital literacy skills into the curriculum to prepare students for the modern workforce.	3.15	Moderately Integrated
4.	promotes cross-curricular connections and integration of knowledge across different subjects.	4.00	Integrated
5.	encourages project-based learning and hands-on experiences to deepen students' understanding of concept.	4.00	Integrated
6.	integrates career readiness and vocational training opportunities into the curriculum to equip students with practical skills.	4.00	Integrated
7.	incorporates community-based learning experiences and partnerships with local organizations.	4.93	Highly Integrated
8.	fosters creativity, innovation, and problem-solving skills among students through integrated learning approaches.	5.00	Highly Integrated
9.	integrates social-emotional learning and character education into academic instruction to support students' holistic development.	5.00	Highly Integrated
10.	encourages to collaborate across disciplines and integrate different perspectives into their teaching practices.	5.00	Highly Integrated
	Overall Mean	4.58	Highly Integrated

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Highly Integrated; 3.40-4.19, Integrated; 2.60-3.39, Moderately Integrated; 1.80-2.59, Less Integrated; 1.00-1.79, Least Integrated

The answers on integrating technology and digital literacy skills into the curriculum to prepare students for the modern workforce got the lowest mean of 3.15, interpreted as moderately integrated. This implies that there are challenges in full implementation of technology to learning sessions. According to participant 2 the lack of sufficient resources to technological gadget limits their integration of this approach in their learning activities. But they are also included in limited times only.

In the study of UNESCO (2020), the essence of the quality context of education has always been a priority as the foundation of the development of learners. However, attention to the concept of quality education has come to the fore as learners, parents and communities, educators, leaders and nations acknowledge that what is learned and how learning occurs are as important as access to education. The provision of important resources like technology is now becoming a must to ensure learners are not left behind. Thus, it must be provided to the context of learning delivery.

Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Balanced

Table 7 presents the extent of integration of the key principles in the implementation of MBHTE school programs in terms of balanced that got an overall mean of 4.57 interpreted as highly integrated. This result shows that schools have been providing balanced learning activities to meet the different factors of learning. The provision of a curriculum that meets the needs, an educational environment that promises learning, and teachers who are qualified and competent. The provision of balanced education services can meet the needs of students in physical, mental and social aspect.

The research of Cummings (2020) expounded the reason for providing balanced education services. This can be a way to provide quality education that meets the development needs of students. This can make them learn all necessary aspects of learning. Learning must include development of skills, knowledge and attitude.

All of the respondents answered that the statement about integration of principles of cultural sensitivity and inclusivity in the school programs implementation, emphasizes the values of respect and tolerance towards diverse perspectives and backgrounds and prioritizes the holistic development of students, including their intellectual, emotional, and social well-being that got the highest mean of 5.00 interpreted as highly integrated. This means that the schools had been compliance with the guidelines to ensure learning activities are centered to all needs of students. This can promote a holistic growth and development.

According to Iqbal (2020) programs of the schools in BARMM are centered towards total learning outcome. This means that moral and academic aspect of development are integrated in the curriculum. There are different learning goals that must be included in the learning strategies of teachers.

The table further reveals that the statement about it encourages collaboration, teamwork, and leadership development among students (4.72), incorporates principles of equity and fairness in providing educational opportunities for all students (4.50), integrates principles of gender equality and women's empowerment in their curriculum and activities (4.50), promotes critical thinking, creativity, and innovation among students (4.48) and integrates principles of environmental sustainability and stewardship in their educational initiatives (4.22) are all highly integrated. This result shows that a balanced consideration of the needs of learners is incorporated in the activities of the students. This can promote holistic growth and development to students.

However, the answers on fostering a sense of community and civic responsibility among students and promoting lifelong learning skills and a growth mindset among students both got the lowest mean of 4.00, interpreted as integrated. This answer aligns with the response

of Participant 6, who shared that the students were provided with activities on lifelong learning as well as community cultivation. However, the concept of academics is the major focus of their learning activities. Although it is a part of the topics in their learning sessions.

According to Poulou (2017) the interactions of teachers and students towards implanting lifelong learning is an important part of quality education. The provision of balanced learning in academic and lifelong learning must be sustained to have well-equipped students with not only knowledge but also skills and the right values to face the community.

Table 7. *Extent of Integration of The Key Principles In The Implementation of MBHTE School Programs in terms of Balance (n = 378)*

	Item	Mean	Interpretation
	<i>The teacher....</i>		
1.	integrates principles of cultural sensitivity and inclusivity in the school programs implementation.	5.00	Highly Integrated
2.	emphasizes the values of respect and tolerance towards diverse perspectives and backgrounds.	5.00	Highly Integrated
3.	incorporates principles of equity and fairness in providing educational opportunities for all students.	4.50	Highly Integrated
4.	prioritizes the holistic development of students, including their intellectual, emotional, and social well-being.	5.00	Highly Integrated
5.	promotes critical thinking, creativity, and innovation among students.	4.48	Highly Integrated
6.	integrates principles of environmental sustainability and stewardship in their educational initiatives.	4.22	Highly Integrated
7.	fosters a sense of community and civic responsibility among students.	4.00	Integrated
8.	promotes lifelong learning skills and a growth mindset among students.	4.00	Integrated
9.	integrates principles of gender equality and women's empowerment in their curriculum and activities.4.50	4.50	Highly Integrated
10.	encourages collaboration, teamwork, and leadership development among students.4.72	4.72	Highly Integrated
	Overall Mean	4.57	Highly Integrated

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Highly Integrated; 3.40-4.19, Integrated; 2.60-3.39, Moderately Integrated; 1.80-2.59, Less Integrated; 1.00-1.79, Least Integrated

The challenges Encountered in the Integration of Key Principles in the Implementation of MBHTE School Programs

The common themes that emerged during interview shows there are minimal problems encountered by the teachers. These included challenges in adequate resources specially technology equipment and competency and integration of lifelong learning as balanced to academic aspects of learning. Some of the discussions are presented in the succeeding significant statements.

According to Participant 4 :

"My experience is that there is lack of sufficient resources, we have limited technology equipment so we conduct this kind of activities not all the time."

Similarly, Participant 6 shared:

"I encountered lack of sufficient resources like gadget to my students so I can not decide to use this mode of learning."

This means that there are problems when implementing technology based learning. The adequacy of resources is vital to the conduct of learning activities.

This agrees with Doney (2023) who explained that adequate resources is vital for effective learning sessions. To ensure children coped with learning activities they must have resources on this approach like gadgets for technological learning. The presence of gadget is a strong driver for students engagement.

Also Participant 11 and 15 shared:

"There is a problem with resources sometimes we have inadequate supply."

The same view was explained by Participant 10 who verbalized that:

"Kulang po kami sa gamit minsan, kaya limited yung activity na pinipili naming para lahat mka join." (We do not have adequate resources so we have limited choices of activities.)

This answer confirms that there are challenges in availability of resources. This can hamper the instructional delivery since some of the students may not have equal access of such references.

In the Report of MBHTE (2020) despite of its effort to provide all needed resources due to the large number of students, still the allocated budget is not sufficient. Although the minister is trying to ask for bigger budget.

Meanwhile Participant 1 and 6 both shared that :

"My experience is that there is lesser integration of lifelong learning when compared to lifelong learning. But we try our best to integrate them in the lessons we make regardless of subjects."

This answer shows that there is challenge in balancing the different topics to be integrated in the learning sessions. The provision of lifelong learning is vital in preparing students to the future.

According to Li, et al (2021) successful implementation of lifelong learning is a unique integration of day to day activity to learning topics and needs of each context. Furthermore, the concept of lifelong learning is closely connected to the idea of culturally responsive pedagogy. Culturally responsive pedagogy, that can prepare the learners to the future demand of society.

Conclusions

The study concludes that the Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education (MBHTE) is effective in implementing key principles that protect the welfare of students. These principles are anchored in the moral governance of the Bangsamoro government, which is committed to providing accessible and quality education. The inclusive and equitable school services have helped students feel safe and motivated to attend school. Furthermore, strict compliance with rights-based education services ensures that children are safe within the school environment. The implementation of the curriculum as mandated by law, along with the balanced integration of services, promotes the welfare of students in the teaching and learning process. However, challenges such as a lack of sufficient materials and equipment for technology integration in instruction, and the need to develop teacher competencies, can hinder the achievement of the goals of school programs. Strengthening the integration of lifelong learning in teacher instruction is essential to prepare students to be competitive in the future.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed: The MBHTE should allocate a budget to upgrade the technological equipment in schools as part of urgent programs, recognizing that technology is vital for improving the quality of instruction and is a basic need for competitiveness in a highly globalized society. Non-governmental partners are encouraged to provide logistical assistance, especially to schools in special geographic areas, to enhance their capacity to deliver quality education, particularly in terms of technological resources. This support would directly address the needs of students, increasing their interest and engagement. School heads should monitor and guide teachers closely in integrating balanced academic and lifelong skills programs to help develop students holistically. The integration of lifelong learning into students' development will prepare them for future roles as productive citizens.

Parents are encouraged to strengthen their collaboration with schools by providing feedback on implemented programs to ensure they protect the welfare and rights of students. Local government officials should support the development of teachers' competencies in implementing the key principles of the MBHTE, ensuring that teachers are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills. Teachers should focus on addressing weak areas in program implementation to provide effective interventions that contribute to the holistic development of students. The national government should continue guiding the MBHTE in providing responsive programs that meet the learning needs of students, thereby harmonizing national education goals with the local contexts of schools in BARMM.

The following research titles are recommended for future studies: "The Regression Analysis of the Core Values of the Education Sector in the Bangsamoro Region," "Exploring the Implementation of Rights-Based Education in the Special Geographic Area in BARMM," and "Financial Competencies of School Heads and Transparency in the Service Delivery of Public Schools in BARMM."

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